

Evaluating the Performance of Passive UHF RFID tags for Traceability of Recycled Concrete Aggregates

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Abstract – The digital transformation of the construction industry is critical to address its significant environmental impacts, which account for 50% of extracted resource consumption, 35% of waste generation, and 5-12% CO₂ emission from construction and renovation activities across Europe. In response to these adverse impacts, the European Union's Green Deal identifies the sector as a priority area to achieve carbon neutrality by 2050. A key enabler of this transformation is materials traceability, which allows monitoring and tracking of materials' origin, composition, and quality across the value chain, facilitating data-driven decision making about material use, reuse, and recycling. Radio frequency identification (RFID) technology offers a contactless solution for such traceability by assigning materials a digital identity in the form of a materials passport (MP). These MPs serve as digital records that assist material tracking and quality assurance. While the approach is broadly applicable to both primary and secondary construction materials, this study focuses on recycled concrete aggregates (RCA) due to their greater importance in circular construction and difficulties associated with verifying their quality and provenance. For this reason, this study evaluates the data transmission characteristics of a passive ultrahigh frequency (UHF) RFID system in RCA to assess its suitability for the traceability application. A compact passive UHF RFID tag was embedded in RCA at depths of 10-40 cm. Its performance was evaluated using a handheld RFID reader by measuring key performance indicators, readability distance (RD), received signal strength indication (RSSI), and tag read count (TRC). To simulate the realistic deployment conditions, the tag-reader orientation was varied at 30-degree intervals over a 360-degree range. The results show that the tag remained detectable under all tested conditions, including different tag-reader orientations and embedding depths within RCA. At depths of 10-20 cm, the tag consistently achieved RD between 80-120 cm with high RSSI and TRC. While readability declined at 30-40 cm depths due to increased signal attenuations and misalignment in orientation, the tag remained readable across all configurations. These findings confirm the feasibility of using a passive UHF RFID system for RCA traceability, allowing for their integration into the digital transformation of circular construction practices.

Keywords: Recycled concrete aggregates, Traceability, Digitalization, RFID technology, Circular construction

1 Introduction

The digital transformation of the construction industry is emerging as an essential component of sustainable development, particularly with regard to material tracking and improved communication of materials quality across their value chain [1–3]. This transition aligns with the broader initiatives to implement circular economy principles, reduce environmental footprints, and boost data-driven decision-making through the integration of reliable data into construction workflows [3]. The construction industry is the largest consumer of natural resources, accounting for approximately 50% of all extracted resources, 35% of the waste generation, and 5-12% of CO₂ emissions across Europe, primarily from construction and renovation activities. Among the key contributors to these impacts are cement and concrete production, which dominate the material use and embodied carbon in buildings [4]. These substantial environmental burdens emphasize the need for sustainable materials management approaches. One promising approach to lower natural resource consumption and related carbon emissions is using recycled concrete aggregates (RCA) in the concrete production.

Despite the potential of RCA to reduce reliance on virgin aggregates and support the closed-loop of the flow of aggregates, its widespread adoption in concrete production remains limited. One of the major obstacles is the absence of transparent and timely communication regarding RCA's quality and performance data for structural applications [5,6]. The heterogeneous nature resulting from diverse demolition sources, processing techniques, and specification of parent concrete makes quality monitoring and tracking a critical requirement before using RCA. The lack of systematic tracking of RCA quality in conventional practices compromises the confidence of stakeholders in using RCA in high-grade applications [2].

The practice of tracking location, history, quality, and application of materials during their lifecycle, referred to as traceability, is gaining recognition as an integral part of sustainable construction [2,7]. By offering a reliable means to monitor materials flow and attributes, traceability supports effective use, recycling, reuse, and quality assurance of both primary and secondary construction materials. The role of traceability is further emphasized by the European Green Deal, which has identified the construction sector as a high-impact sector for achieving climate neutrality by 2050 and called for a fundamental shift in its material management practices. This includes the digitalisation of the materials value chain to document origin, composition, processing history, and quality of construction materials [4].

In this broader framework, a vast stock of aging buildings in Europe offers a substantial reservoir of secondary materials that can be recycled for new construction projects [8]. The demolition of these structures presents an avenue for the large-scale recovery of RCA, contributing to circular construction goals. However, for effective reintegration of these recovered materials into new construction projects, it is necessary to carefully characterize, document, and convey the quality and performance of these recovered materials. Digital traceability tools that connect objects to their information throughout their lifecycle must be implemented to achieve this goal [3]. The digitalisation of recovery, characterisation, and value chain documentation is essential for bringing waste materials from aging buildings back into the construction

value chain, thereby reducing dependencies on virgin resources and minimizing the environmental impact of construction [2,5].

Radiofrequency identification (RFID) offers a potential traceability solution for the construction sector with the opportunity to link materials with their digital information. RFID technology allows wireless, noncontact, automated identification and data capture through tags attached to physical objects. This technology is widely used to improve inventory control, quality assurance, object identification, and tracking in logistics, manufacturing, and healthcare industries [9]. The potential lies in its ability to link physical materials to assign digital identities and store relevant information throughout their lifecycle, a concept referred to as a material passport (MP). The idea of MP was formalized by the EU-funded Building as Materials Banks (BAMB) [10] and has been actively promoted by circular economy initiatives run by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation [11]. MP has also been shown to assist circular construction practices throughout the design, usage, and end-of-life stages by Madaster [12], and Orms [13].

Embedding RFID tags within RCA enables the creation of MP, a digital tool for their traceability, wherein each batch of RCA is uniquely identifiable. The digital identity given by RFID tags can be used to access and update information about RCA linked with an online digital database [5,9]. This information can help in data-driven decision-making during concrete mix design, quality control, materials recycling, and reuse. However, in developing such a tracking system based on RFID, evaluating the performance and reliability of the RFID components is important for the system's effective functioning. The performance consistency and accuracy of data transmission of RFID are affected by factors such as the dielectric properties of the host material, attachment method of the tag, tag-reader orientation, and interference with radio waves from the surrounding environment [9,14–17]. In RCA, these challenges are more pronounced due to the irregular density and granular nature of RCA, which can influence electromagnetic signal propagation, resulting in shorter read range, low signal strength, and inconsistent read rates [18]. To ensure the robust operation of RFID, it is essential to evaluate how these parameters, such as embedding depth in RCA, orientation of the tag, and reading distance, impact the performance of the system. Furthermore, coupling RFID with laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS), a spectral emission-based technique for quality inspection of RCA [19] would allow the integration of quality data into the digital identity, increasing the reliability of reuse decisions and circularity-oriented designs [5].

Therefore, this study aims to evaluate the performance of passive ultrahigh-frequency (UHF) RFID tags embedded in RCA to assess their suitability for digital traceability applications. RCA was sourced from the advanced concrete recycling process of advance dry recovery (ADR), which ensures relatively high-quality aggregate fractions [20]. A Passive UHF tag was embedded at depths of 10 cm, 20 cm, 30 cm, and 40 cm within RCA, and its performance was assessed through three key performance indicators: readability distance (RD), received signal strength indication (RSSI), and tag read count (TRC). These metrics represent the transmission characteristics of the RFID system and provide the basis for its feasibility in the RCA traceability system.

2 RFID-based Traceability of RCA

RFID is a wireless communication system that has become an essential tool for object tracking, automated identification, and supply chain management across various sectors [9]. Its integration into the construction industry is recent but rapidly growing, specifically to enhance traceability and documentation of building materials.[5,21]. A RFID system is composed of three components: a tag, a reader, and a data management system. The interaction between these components and along with their integration with a digital database for traceability application, is illustrated in Figure 1. The tag contains a chip for data storage and an antenna for transmitting signals. The reader emits the signals to activate the tag's chip and receive the data from the tag. Readers include an antenna for transmitting and receiving the signals, a transceiver for processing, and an interface for transferring data. The data management system is the backbone of the RFID operations, enabling the management and processing of the data [9,21]. RFID system functions on different frequency ranges, each tailored for specific applications. These classification and their key characteristics are summarised in Table 1 [5,9].

Table 1: Types of RFID technology based on its frequency bands

RFID Band	Frequency Range	Read Range (m)	Applications	Standards/Protocol
Low frequency (LF)	125-134.2 kHz	Up to 0.5	Animal identification, access control	ISO 18000-2, ISO11784, ISO14223
High frequency (HF)	13.56 MHz	Up to 1	Smart cards, NFC-enabled devices	ISO18000-3, ISO/IEC14443
Ultra-high frequency (UHF)	864-928 MHz	Up to 20	Logistics, Supply chain, Object-level traceability	ISO 18000-6C, EPCglobal Gen 2
Super-high frequency (SHF)	2.4-56 GHz	Up to 100	Toll collection, fleet tracking, and high-speed object detection in transport	No unified standards

In addition to frequency-based classification of RFID technology, RFID tags are also distinguished by their power source, which directly influences their read range, cost, and application suitability. Table 2 provides an overview of active, semi-active, and passive RFID tags, highlighting their functional characteristics, advantages, and limitations for different use cases [9,14,21].

Table 2: Classification of RFID tag types based on power source

Tag Type	Power Source	Range	Applications	Advantages	Limitations
Active	Internal battery (powers the chip and transmission)	Long	Tracking of vehicles and shipping containers	Long-range communication, autonomous operations	High cost, limited life due to the battery
Semi-Active	Internal battery (powers chip only)	Medium	Environmental monitoring	Balanced functionality, suitable for sensor integration	Battery dependent, moderate cost, and maintenance
Passive	No internal battery (powered by reader signals)	Short to medium	Inventory control, object tracking	Low cost, long life span	Shorter range

Passive UHF RFID operates on the electromagnetic waves generated by the reader. The reader's antenna emits radio waves to communicate with the tags. The tag antenna captures this energy, activating its chip, which modulates the received signals to encode its stored data and reflects signals to the reader. The reader decodes these signals for further processing [9]. This seamless communication makes passive UHF RFID

an efficient tool for RCA traceability applications. The communication mechanism between the RFID reader and a passive tag is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of communication between RFID components and their integration with an online database for digital traceability

Three key performance parameters are typically assessed to evaluate the effectiveness of the RFID system under challenging conditions. Received signal strength (RSSI), a measure of the strength of the back-scattered signal received by the reader from the tag, serves as a quality of tag-reader communication. Tag read count (TRC) is the number of detections of a tag in a specific period, reflecting the detection consistency of the system. Readability distance (RD), the maximum range at which a tag is detectable [14,15,21]. These performance metrics are sensitive to the orientation between the tag and the reader's antenna polarisation, along with the dielectric nature of the materials and interference from the surrounding environment [14,16,21]. Tags that aligned with the polarization direction of the reader's electromagnetic waves achieve stronger performance, while misalignment reduces RSSI, TRC, and RD. These effects will be amplified when embedding the tag in RCA, where its orientation is random. To counteract this variability, the circularly polarized antenna is a suitable option that improves tag performance regardless of the orientation [14]. Assessing this metric in RCA conditions is critical for validating the robustness and practical feasibility of the RFID-based traceability system in the construction industry.

Figure 2: Wireless communication between the RFID reader and the passive UHF tag

3 Methodology

To evaluate the performance of an RFID system for RCA tracking, an experiment was conducted by embedding RFID tag at varying depths inside a heap of recycled concrete aggregates. The experimental system was designed to assess how factors such as embedding depth, tag-reader orientation influence the RD, RSSI, and TRC. These parameters are important for determining the successful detection and reliability of RFID tags in RCA, providing insight for developing an RFID-based traceability system.

3.1 RFID System

A passive UHF RFID system operating within the European Telecommunication Standards Institute (ETSI) frequency band (865-868 MHz) was selected for its cost-effectiveness, extended life, and applicability to supply chain management [9]. The RFID tag utilized was a commercially available UHF passive tag measuring 10 mm x 8 mm x 5 mm, compliant with EPC Gen2 and ISO/IEC 18000-6C standards. The tag incorporates Alien Higgs 3 EPC Class 1 Gen 2 integrated circuit (IC) because of its reliability in challenging conditions. For the performance evaluation of the tag, a UHF RFID sled reader was utilized, which features a Cortex-M3 MCU (microcontroller unit) and a 4 dBic circular polarized antenna, ensuring high sensitivity, robust performance, multi-tag reading capabilities, and data collection from tags. The selected RFID tags and handheld reader are shown in Figure 3. The reader operated within the EU frequency range, supporting C1 GEN 2 / ISO 18000-6C protocols and at an output power level of 30 dBm [9,16].

3.2 Experimental procedures

To investigate the effect of embedding depth on RFID performance, the tag was embedded at depths of 10 cm, 20 cm, 30 cm, and 40 cm in cylindrical containers filled with recycled concrete aggregates. Measurements were taken at an interval of 20 cm, gradually increasing the distance between the reader and the embedded tag at each orientation. This setup aims to simulate the industrial conditions [14] where, during the handling of aggregates, the orientation and location of RFID tags can vary unpredictably [18].

For each orientation, readability distance, the RSSI, and TRC were recorded to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the system's performance. Data from these experiments was analysed to identify trends and optimize RFID configuration in recycled concrete aggregates [14,15,22]. The experimental setup for performance evaluation, including schematic and laboratory implementation, is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Selected RFID reader and the tags for RCA traceability

Figure 4: RFID performance measurement setup (left) Schematic, (right) laboratory setup

4 Results and Discussion

The experimental evaluation demonstrated that both embedding depth and tag reader orientation significantly impact the readability and reliability of the passive UHF RFID tag embedded within RCA. Despite the challenging environment presented by the dense and dielectric nature of RCA, the RFID system maintained effective performance with the tag remaining readable at a distance of 50 cm under the least favourable condition. These findings highlight the system's robustness and support its feasibility for industrial application of RCA traceability.

4.1 Effect of Embedding Depth on RFID Performance

The embedding of RFID tag in RCA emerged as a key factor that significantly affected the system performance. As seen in the Figure 5 the tag embedded at 10 cm RCA depth demonstrated the highest RD values with near-complete angular coverage and consistent detection up to 120 cm distance. As the depth increased to 20 cm and 30 cm, RD values declined moderately but remained sufficient for readability. However, at 40 cm depth, the performance dropped significantly, especially at misaligned angles, with RD values ranging from 100 cm to 50 cm [14,15]

Figure 5: Readability of RFID tag at each RCA depth and orientation

As RD, RSSI, and TRC are interlinked, changes in embedding depth directly influence the signal strength and the system's ability to detect the tag. Figure 6 shows the expected trend between the RD value and the RSSI value at the 0-degree orientation between the reader and the tag [14,21]. An increase in RD reduces RSSI due to signal attenuation over distance. However, with an increase in embedding depth, the decline in RSSI value becomes more significant. For instance, at the RCA depth of 10 cm, the RSSI value ranged between -60 dBm to -72.5 dBm. However, at the RCA depth of 40 cm, RSSI dropped below -75 dBm at the RD value of 100 cm, and beyond it decreased immensely that the tag was undetectable.

Figure 6: Reduction in RSSI of RFID tag at 0° orientation across the embedding depth

Similarly, Figure 7 displays the direct relation between RD, RSS, and TRC at an embedding depth of 20 cm. As RSSI decreases with an increase in RD and embedding depth, TRC also declines. The highest TRC, typically 12-14 detections, was recorded at shorter RD with strong RSSI values. As RD increased and RSSI declined, the TRC value declined to 6 detections when RSSI fell to -75 dBm [22].

This decline in measurement of performance metrics indicates that the materials' thickness and dielectric factor of RCA can impair the RFID signals, readability. These results emphasize the importance of selected RFID tags and their placement to preserve communication reliability, which is important for traceability applications.

4.2 Effect of Change in Orientation on Readability and Reliability

Tag-reader orientation was a critical determination of readability and reliability. Figure 5 represents RD at all four embedding depths across the full 360 angular range with an interval of 30 degrees. It is evident from the figure that orientation plays an important role in the RFID system's performance. Tag aligned with the reader's polarization axis achieved greater RD compared to oblique angles. For instance, at 10 cm depth, RD remained 80-140 cm across most angles. While at 40 cm embedding depth, RD dropped below 100 cm at aligned angles and was readable up to 50 cm at oblique angles. Further evidence of the orientation effect is provided in Figure 7, where a fluctuation in the TRC value of 11 to 14 can be observed depending on the orientation at the RD of 20 cm, and a change in RSSI is also visible through the heatmap. Similarly, at RD of 80 cm, the fluctuation in TRC is observed between 12-8, with tag losing detectability at some oblique angles. This is due to the combined effect of embedding depth, higher RD, and unfavourable orientation.

This parallel decrease in TRC and change in RSSI confirm the effect of angular alignment on signal strength and readability, and detection consistency [14,15,21,22].

Figure 7: Read consistency of the tag at 20 cm RCA depth in relation to RSSI and RD at each orientation

These results collectively demonstrate that both embedding depth and tag-reader orientation are critical determinants of passive UHF RFID systems in RCA, directly impacting signal strength, read range, and detection accuracy. The challenges highlighted the importance of selection an RFID system with sufficient signal strength, optimisation of tag placement, and navigating the reader based on the tag's orientation

5 Conclusion

This study assessed the transmission characteristics of a passive UHF RFID tag embedded in RCA to evaluate its suitability for digital traceability within the construction workflow. The results show that readability, signal strength, and detection rate are influenced by embedding depth, tag-reader orientation; however, the tag remained detectable under these challenging conditions. The long service life of passive RFID, along with its compatibility with digital platforms, such as cloud databases, building information modelling (BIM), and blockchain, offers secure and real-time tracking of the construction materials value chain [1,9,16]. This work is part of a broader, ongoing investigation of the RFID system for traceability of concrete materials. Future efforts are focused on evaluating the durability of RFID tags against the physical stresses they can face during the materials lifecycle.

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